

Another 4Q14 fragment (IAA Plate 1087 frg. 6)

Eibert Tigchelaar

KU Leuven

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Recently I identified the text and location of two unidentified 4Q14 fragments (4Q14 frags. 37 and 41), and added to 4Q14 two fragments from PAM 43.677 that had not yet been associated with 4Q14.¹ After the publication of those fragments I stumbled upon yet another 4Q14 fragment which apparently had already been identified as an Exodus fragment by an earlier editor, but had never been placed with the other 4Q14 fragments, and had not been published in the official edition.²

The Israel Antiquities Authority (IAA) Museum Plate 1087 contains a strange mixture of fragments, to wit 4Q30 frags. 12, 14, 15, 26, 27, 43, and 44; 4Q33 7, 13, 14, and 15, as well as in the top two rows of the plate seven fragments with text that apparently was identified as Pentateuchal, some of which which do not seem to have been published in the DJD series.

The top left fragment of IAA Museum Plate 1087 was previously placed on Museum Plate 71, which was photographed on PAM 43.680. In the DJD 33 volume it was numbered PAM 43.680 frag. 7.³ I identified this fragment as an unpublished 4Q13 manuscript,⁴ but apparently the editor who had transferred the fragment to Plate 1087 had already identified its text as corresponding to Exodus.

Some of the other probably unpublished Plate 1087 fragments are hard to read or to identify, but on the basis of the recent IAA photograph the most right fragment of the second row can easily be identified textually and materially.⁵ It fits in 4Q14 col. VIII in lines 23 and 24, and perhaps even has the extreme bottom tip of the right leg of the second *he* of יהוה of line 22. The fragment joins col. VIII in line 22, and provides a few more words of Exod 17:14–16.

¹Eibert Tigchelaar, "Improving the Edition of 4Q14 (4QExod^c)," *Textus* 30 (2021): 179-86. doi: 10.1163/2589255X-bja10018.

²Judith E. Sanderson, "14. 4QExod^c," in *Qumran Cave 4.VII: Genesis to Numbers*, DJD 12 (Oxford: Clarendon, 1994), 97-125.

³Dana M. Pike and Andrew C. Skinner, *Qumran Cave 4.XXIII: Unidentified Fragments*, DJD 33 (Oxford: Clarendon, 2001), Pl. XXI.

⁴Eibert Tigchelaar, "On the Unidentified Fragments of DJD XXXIII and PAM 43.680: A New Manuscript of 4QNarrative and Poetic Composition, and Fragments of 4Q13, 4Q269, 4Q525 and 4Q5b (?)," *Revue de Qumran* 21/83 (2004): 477-85, at 483.

⁵This fragment image has not yet been uploaded to the Leon Levy Dead Sea Scrolls Digital Library, but is available from the Israel Antiquities Authority.

4Q14 Col. VIII lines 22-24 (Exod 17:14-16); text of IAA Plate 1087 frg 6 in red

- | | |
|---|----|
| [ו]יאמר יהוה אל משה כתב זאת זכרון בספר ושי[ם באזני י]הושע[כי]מחא ⁶ | 22 |
| [אמחה]את זכר[ע]מלק מתחת השמים ויבן[משה מזבח ויקרא שמו יהוה] | 23 |
| [נסי וי]אמר כי י[ד ע]ל[ן כס יה מלח]מה ליהוה בעמל[ק מדר דר vacat | 24 |

section of 4Q14 col. VIII
(screenshot from <https://www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-371013>)
and IAA Plate 1087 frag. 6 (IAA photograph)
photographer Shai Halevi

⁶I differ from the DJD edition in reading all letters of יהוה in line 22, and at the end of the same line מחא rather than מחה. The reconstructions in line 24 are according to the Masoretic Text, but the variant wordings of the Samaritan Pentateuch would also be possible.